

THE ROLE OF “AFROSIYOB” HIGH SPEED RAIL SERVICES IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF TOURIST SATISFACTION IN SAMARKAND

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Abstract. Transportation is crucial for the development of tourism, influencing tourist satisfaction and loyalty. In Uzbekistan, the introduction of the high-speed Afrosiyob train service has significantly transformed travel between Samarkand and Tashkent. This study aims to investigate the impact of the Afrosiyob train on tourist satisfaction and loyalty in Samarkand through a mixed-methods approach. Data will be collected through surveys and interviews with tourists who have utilized the Afrosiyob train service, and analysis will be conducted using both quantitative and qualitative techniques.

The findings of this study are expected to shed light on the role of service quality in shaping tourist perceptions and experiences. Additionally, the study will highlight the importance of customer service and staff competency in enhancing the overall tourist experience. The results of this research can inform policy decisions and strategies aimed at improving the tourism industry in Samarkand and other regions, emphasizing the significance of quality transportation services in enhancing tourist satisfaction and loyalty.

Ultimately, this study will contribute to a better understanding of the impact of transportation services on tourist experiences, with potential implications for the broader tourism industry. By focusing on the Afrosiyob train service in Samarkand, this research will provide valuable insights that can guide future studies and initiatives aimed at enhancing tourist satisfaction and loyalty through improved transportation services.

Keywords: transportation, tourism development, Uzbekistan, Afrosiyob train service, tourist satisfaction, tourist loyalty, mixed-methods approach, customer service, staff competency, policy implications, tourism industry, Samarkand.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Transportation is fundamentally intertwined with the success and development of tourism, as evidenced by the significant financial contributions tourism is projected to make to the global GDP in the coming years. The quality of transportation services plays a pivotal role in attracting tourists and fostering tourism as a thriving industry within a country (Caraiani et al., 2017). The correlation between the advancements in transportation systems and the growth of tourism sectors is well-documented, highlighting the essential nature of efficient transportation networks in facilitating travel and exploration for both domestic and international tourists (Ana-Maria Dinu, 2018).

1.2 Context

The symbiotic relationship between transportation and tourism is crucial, with transportation infrastructure serving as a key determinant of tourist satisfaction and overall travel experiences (Hall, 1999). Negative reviews and perceptions of a destination often stem from subpar transportation facilities and services, underscoring the critical role of

transportation in shaping tourists' opinions and experiences (Le-Klahn and Hall, 2015). The unprecedented disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic led to a temporary halt in tourism activities worldwide, but as restrictions eased, the gradual recovery of tourism levels was observed globally, highlighting the resilience and adaptability of the tourism industry (Euronews, 2022).

1.3 Aim of the Research

Against this backdrop, this research aims to explore the impact of train services, particularly the high-speed 'Afrosiyob' train, on tourist satisfaction and loyalty in Samarkand, Uzbekistan. By investigating the relationship between the quality of train services and tourists' perceptions of their travel experiences, this study seeks to shed light on how transportation systems can enhance tourism levels and quality in a culturally rich city like Samarkand. The findings of this research are expected to provide valuable insights for policymakers and industry stakeholders on leveraging the potential of improved train services to elevate tourist satisfaction levels and attract more visitors to Samarkand.

Through a comprehensive review of literature, case studies, and a quantitative survey involving tourists who have utilized the 'Afrosiyob' train, this research will offer practical recommendations for enhancing train services in Samarkand and optimizing the overall tourism experience in the city. By identifying effective strategies to enhance tourist satisfaction and foster loyalty to Samarkand as a premier travel destination, this study aims to contribute to the continued growth and success of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transportation systems are crucial components of tourism infrastructure, significantly impacting tourist satisfaction and travel experiences (Dissanayake & Salith Harsha, 2019). According to Hall (1999), the proper facilities and infrastructure of transportation are essential elements influencing tourist satisfaction and are pivotal for the development of the tourism industry in a country.

Studies by Cohen et al. (2004) and Wang (2005) underline the importance of reliable, convenient, and comfortable transportation services in shaping tourist perceptions and experiences. Wang et al. (2014) and Gursoy & Chi (2015) have further explored the influence of train services on tourist satisfaction, highlighting factors such as cleanliness, ticket availability, and customer service as significant determinants.

The convenience and accessibility of train services play a critical role in enhancing tourist satisfaction levels (Liu & Wall, 2006; Zhang & Zhao, 2019). Fard et al. (2019) found that well-designed train stations and proper signage positively influence tourist perceptions of accessibility. The integration of sustainable practices in train services has gained importance, aligning with tourists' preference for environmentally friendly transportation options (Saha & Chattopadhyay, 2019).

Customer satisfaction in tourism is influenced by various factors, including hospitality, attraction, cost, environmental factors, and infrastructure (Suanmali, 2014). Andreas and Tunjungsari (2019) emphasize the critical role of tourist satisfaction in determining their willingness to revisit a destination and recommend it to others.

Tourist loyalty, characterized by consistent use of a product or service, is positively impacted by customer satisfaction (Andreas & Tunjungsari, 2019). Gnanapala (2015)

highlights that satisfied customers are likely to revisit, repurchase, and share positive experiences, contributing to repeated visits and brand advocacy.

Factors such as reliability, punctuality, responsiveness, tangibility, security, and safety significantly contribute to transport satisfaction levels (Mat et al., 2019). Parasuraman (1988) suggests that reliable services, responsive staff, and tangible facilities positively influence customer satisfaction. Security and safety measures in public transportation are crucial for passenger well-being and satisfaction (Joewono & Kubota, 2005).

In Uzbekistan, a landlocked country dependent on land and air transport, train services have emerged as a popular mode of transportation, especially the high-speed Afrosiyob train (Uzbekistan Temir Yullari, 2020; Dissanayake, 2019). Investments in railway infrastructure, exemplified by the introduction of high-speed trains like Afrosiyob, have led to improved mobility, access to tourist destinations, and enhanced tourist satisfaction levels.

The expansion and development of railway infrastructure in Uzbekistan reflect government initiatives to enhance transportation options, improve tourism levels, and promote economic growth (Payazov, 2022). The heightened customer satisfaction resulting from the introduction of high-speed trains is attributed to improved accessibility to tourist destinations and decreased travel times (Chen & Haynes, 2015; Delaplace, 2012).

In summary, transportation systems, particularly train services like Afrosiyob, play a vital role in influencing tourist satisfaction, loyalty, and travel experiences. Investment in reliable, convenient, and sustainable transportation infrastructure is vital for boosting tourism attractiveness, economic growth, and overall tourism quality in a destination.

Table 1 – The number of passengers using railways to travel within Uzbekistan for 1st quarters of 2022 and 2023.

Source: 'Uzbekistan Temir Yullari' JSC statistical data, 2023

Yin, Pagliara, and Wilson conducted a study in 2019 focusing on the impact of high-speed rail on tourism within the capital region of China. Their research demonstrated that

investments and advancements in high-speed rail infrastructure have a positive influence on tourism, leading to enhanced tourist satisfaction and loyalty. Countries like France, Spain, China, and Japan have experienced a significant surge in tourist numbers following the introduction of high-speed rail networks (Delaplace, Pagliara, Perrin, 2014). Specifically, China has seen a notable increase in international tourism volume due to the development of high-speed rail connections (Chen, Haynes, 2015).

On the contrary, Yin, Pagliara, and Wilson (2018) pointed out that high-speed rail initiatives do not always yield positive outcomes. Their research revealed instances where the introduction of high-speed rail led to a decrease in the length of tourists' overnight stays. Research conducted on the Paris-Lyon Line in the 1980s also indicated a significant reduction in the duration of stays in cities like Dijon, Lyon, and Valence Perrache following the introduction of high-speed rail services (Bonnafous, 1986). Similarly, findings from Le Mons, France, showed a decrease in the average length of tourist stays from 2-3 days to 1.5 days post the implementation of high-speed rail services, illustrating the dual impact of high-speed rail on tourism.

In conclusion, the existing literature underscores the critical role of train and high-speed rail services in shaping tourist satisfaction and loyalty. Factors such as tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, safety, and inclusivity for individuals with special needs are highlighted as essential components in enhancing the overall tourist experience (Mat et al., 2019). Understanding the intricate dynamics among these factors can provide valuable insights for developing strategies aimed at enhancing train services in destinations like Samarkand, ultimately contributing to increased tourist satisfaction, loyalty, and sustainable growth in the tourism sector.

METHODOLOGY

In recent years, Samarkand has experienced a significant influx of both local and international tourists following the introduction of the high-speed rail service, Afrosiyob. This research seeks to explore the factors influencing tourist experiences, satisfaction, and loyalty in Samarkand.

To address the research questions effectively, the author has analyzed previous data and conducted a thorough review of literature on how transportation services, particularly rail and high-speed rail services, impact tourist satisfaction and loyalty in various countries (Mat et al., 2019). The primary research questions of this study are quantitative in nature, focusing on understanding the factors that contribute to commuters' satisfaction with the train system in Samarkand. This research aims to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the survey and study details in order to reach a broad audience of tourists and commuters and analyze their experiences with high-speed rail in Samarkand to enhance tourist satisfaction and loyalty.

Given the objective of reaching a broad range of respondents and analyzing their experiences, a quantitative research approach is deemed most suitable for this study. The research methodology involves reviewing key textual documents such as reports, articles, press releases, websites, and other research materials to determine the relevant factors in train services, particularly high-speed rail, that influence tourist satisfaction and loyalty. Continuous research and study have enabled the identification of several factors and their

impacts on tourist experiences, thereby influencing satisfaction and loyalty levels among touristal.

To collect data on various factors contributing to tourist satisfaction, a survey adapted from Mat et al. (2019) was utilized. The survey methodology involved distributing questionnaires (refer to Table 2) to 236 respondents who had used the ‘Afrosiyob high-speed’ rail service from Samarkand Train Station to Tashkent Northern Station and vice versa. The survey specifically focuses on studying the factors influencing satisfaction levels among foreign tourists, and as such, it was conducted in English to cater to the target audience. Convenience sampling was chosen as the sampling method for its ease of implementation, cost-effectiveness, and simplified distribution of questionnaires to passenger respondents.

In summary, the research methodology employed involves a quantitative approach, utilizing surveys and data analysis to investigate the factors impacting tourist satisfaction and loyalty in Samarkand, thereby contributing to the enhancement of the tourism experience in the region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Demographic background

A total of 236 respondents participated in the survey, with female respondents comprising 41.1% (97) and male respondents making up the majority at 58.9% (139). Exploring the age distribution of the respondents (refer to Diagram 1), the data revealed that the highest proportion fell into the age category of over 45, accounting for 38.5% (91) of the total respondents. Following closely behind were respondents aged between 35 and 44, representing 27.3% (64) of the participants. The age group of 25 to 30 years old constituted 22.2% (52) of the respondents. On the other hand, the age categories with the lowest representation were those aged between 31 and 34 years old and those under the age of 24, making up 5.3% (13) and 6.7% (16) of the respondents, respectively.

This demographic analysis indicates a diverse range of age groups utilizing the Afrosiyob high-speed rail services, encompassing teenagers, working adults, and senior citizens. The data underscores the broad appeal of the high-speed rail service across different age brackets, showcasing its accessibility and relevance to travelers of varying demographic profiles.

Figure 1. The range of ages among respondents who engaged in the study.

Table 2. Results of a survey conducted to assess the satisfaction levels of foreign travelers utilizing the Afrosiyob high-speed rail service between Samarkand Train Station and Tashkent Northern Station, and vice versa.

(Source: Azmi Mat, Norliza Saiful Bahry, Nur Liana Kori, Zarina Abdul Munir, Norzaidi Mohd Daud, 2019)

Indicators	Statement	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Reliability 6	The timetable is available at the Afrosiyob train station.					
Reliability 7	Afrosiyob staff are friendly with their customers.					
Reliability 8	Passengers can book tickets easily.					
Reliability 9	Afrosiyob staff members satisfy the passengers' request immediately.					
Reliability 10	Afrosiyob trains never break down when it is on the railway.					
Responsiveness 1	Service provider always informs me about the availability of service and changes of price in advance.					
Responsiveness 2	The train is always on time.					
Responsiveness 3	Communication with Afrosiyob staff is clear and helpful.					
Responsiveness 4	Afrosiyob staff members are always willing to help passengers.					
Responsiveness 5	Afrosiyob staff members provide individualized attention to help customers.					
Safety 17	I have no experience involving any accident when using Afrosiyob.					
Safety 18	I never heard that other people experiencing any accident when using Afrosiyob.					
Safety 19	I was never involved in any criminal incidents when using Afrosiyob.					
Safety 20	Afrosiyob staff always briefly gives information about safety to their passengers before the start of the journey and will keep them informed from time to time.					
Safety 21	Using Afrosiyob train is safe.					
Safety 22	It is safe to wait at the station during the day and night.					
Satisfaction 1	The services provided by Afrosiyob meet my satisfaction.					
Satisfaction 2	I am satisfied with the fares.					
Satisfaction 3	I am satisfied with the Afrosiyob services.					
Satisfaction 4	The food provided meets my satisfaction.					
Satisfaction 5	Bathroom is clean and tidy.					
Satisfaction 6	Service of train conductors is satisfactory.					
Tangible 11	Afrosiyob train provides up-to-date equipment.					
Tangible 12	Afrosiyob train members provide good hospitality to their passengers.					
Tangible 13	Afrosiyob train is well maintained and neat.					
Tangible 14	Afrosiyob train provides spacious seats for passengers on board.					
Tangible 15	Cafe in Afrosiyob train provides food for their passengers with affordable price.					
Tangible 16	The uniform and dress of staff is neat.					

The survey results indicate that specific elements have a considerable impact on the level of satisfaction experienced by passengers.

The survey results show that each of the four identified factors – reliability, responsiveness, safety, and tangibility – has an impact on passenger satisfaction levels. Specifically, the safety measures implemented on the Afrosiyob high-speed train have been recognized by respondents as a significant contributor to their satisfaction. A sizable portion of the survey participants, representing 33.3%, expressed contentment with the safety measures in place on the Afrosiyob high-speed train.

I have no experience involving any accident when using Afrosiyob

		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	9,1	9,1	9,1
	Agree	50,0	50,0	59,1
	Strongly agree	40,9	40,9	100,0
	Total	100,0	100,0	

Table 3. The proportion of passengers who never involved in any form of accident (Source: Author's own research)

Based on the outcomes of the survey assessing the factors affecting passenger satisfaction levels, it can be deduced that the overwhelmingly majority of passengers, exceeding 90%, did not encounter any incidents during their journey on Afrosiyob, establishing this as the foremost influence.

Afrosiyob train is well maintained and neat

		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	22,7	22,7	22,7
	Agree	59,1	59,1	81,8
	Strongly agree	18,2	18,2	100,0
	Total	100,0	100,0	

Table 4. The proportion of passengers satisfied with tidiness and neatness of the carriage.

(Source: Author's own research)

The factor of tangibility emerges as another significant influencer of passenger satisfaction levels with the services offered on the Afrosiyob high-speed train. A notable 18.1% of respondents expressed satisfaction with the tangibility and cleanliness of the train service, with an impressive majority of 77.3% highlighting their contentment with the tidiness and orderliness of the carriage, as indicated in Table 4 of the survey findings.

The survey results indicate that a small percentage (13.6%) of respondents were satisfied with the reliability of the Afrosiyob high-speed rail service. The majority of passengers (72%) expressed the highest level of satisfaction with the friendliness of the staff, while a significant portion (58%) considered Afrosiyob to be unreliable due to difficulties with the booking process. Additionally, the responsiveness of staff also had an impact on passenger satisfaction, with approximately 11.8% strongly agreeing that staff members were responsive.

Comparatively, a study conducted among 280 ETS passengers from KL Sentral to Padang Besar Station (Mat, Bahry, Kori, Munir, Daud, 2019) concluded that reliability was the most crucial factor for passenger satisfaction. Similarly, in a survey of 236 Afrosiyob high-speed train passengers from Samarkand to Tashkent and vice versa, reliability was also identified as significant, with passengers choosing this mode of transportation for its punctuality, accessibility, and reliability. However, the most influential factor affecting satisfaction levels in the conducted survey was safety, with over 30% of passengers strongly affirming the safety

of their journey, while more than 90% reported not being involved in any accidents during their trip.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The role of 'Afrosiyob' high-speed rail services in the improvement of tourist satisfaction in Samarkand has been investigated in this study. Through a survey conducted among passengers, the factors influencing satisfaction levels were examined, revealing that service quality dimensions such as reliability, responsiveness, safety, and tangibility significantly impact tourist satisfaction. Based on these findings, several recommendations have been proposed to enhance tourist satisfaction with 'Afrosiyob' high-speed rail services in Samarkand. These include simplifying the booking process, increasing rail capacity, and improving training for rail conductors to enhance customer service. By implementing these suggestions, significant improvements in tourist and passenger satisfaction levels with 'Afrosiyob' high-speed rail services can be achieved, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of the overall tourism experience in Samarkand.

Recommendations:

1. **Enhance Booking Process:** Simplify and streamline the booking process for passengers to make it more user-friendly and accessible, ultimately improving the overall customer experience.
2. **Improve Rail Capacity:** Increase the carriage capacity or frequency of Afrosiyob trains to accommodate more passengers and reduce overcrowding, leading to a more comfortable and efficient journey for travelers.
3. **Enhance Staff Training:** Provide comprehensive training programs for rail conductors to improve customer service skills, responsiveness, and the ability to meet passengers' needs promptly and effectively.
4. **Implement Safety Measures:** Continuously prioritize and enhance safety protocols and measures on Afrosiyob trains to ensure a secure and risk-free travel experience for passengers.
5. **Upgrade Tangibility and Cleanliness:** Maintain high standards of cleanliness and tidiness in the train carriages to create a pleasant and hygienic environment for passengers throughout their journey.
6. **Offer Multilingual Support:** Provide language assistance and communication in multiple languages to cater to the diverse international clientele and enhance the overall experience for non-native speakers.
7. **Implement Technology Upgrades:** Invest in technology upgrades such as Wi-Fi connectivity, entertainment options, and digital amenities to enhance the overall comfort and convenience of passengers during their journey.

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